

List of events organised by the Romanian Society for Bioinformatics between November 2017 and April 2024

Event	Dates	Host institution	Link	In person / online
1st RoBioinfo: Perspectives of bioinformatics in Romania	24 Nov 2017	Babes Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca	https://rsbi.ro/evenimente/1st-romanian-bioinformatics-seminar/	In person
2nd RoBioinfo:	18-20 April 2018	Institute of Biochemistry, Bucharest	NA	In person
3rd RoBioinfo: Next-Generation Sequencing Data Analysis	15-16 November 2018	West University, Timișoara	https://tinyurl.com/robioinfo3	In person
4th RoBioinfo: Next-Generation Sequencing Technologies	25-27 February 2019	University of Bucharest	NA	In person
5th RoBioinfo: Bioinformatics tools for exploring protein biology	4-5 April 2019	Alexandra Ioan Cuza University, Iasi	https://tinyurl.com/robioinfo5	In person
6th @RoBioinfo Seminar: Machine Learning for Biology	5-6 October 2019	Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca	https://tinyurl.com/robioinfo6	In person
7th @RoBioinfo Seminar – Human DNA variants:	7-8 October 2019	UMF Cluj-Napoca	https://tinyurl.com/robioinfo7	In person

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from functional annotation to disease association				
Webinar series: National bioinformatics communities in ELIXIR	24 September, 29 September and 6 October 2020	ELIXIR Hub	https://elixir-europe.org/events/webinar-elixir-romania	online
8th @RoBioinfo Seminar: Study of Antimicrobial Resistance using Genomics	4 November 2020	RSBI	https://tinyurl.com/robioinfo8	online
9th @RoBioinfo Seminar: Metagenomics	12-13 April 2021	RSBI	https://tinyurl.com/robioinfo9	online
10th @RoBioinfo Seminar: NGS Data Analysis	June 2021	RSBI	NA	online
11th @RoBioinfo Seminar: Cancer Genomics	21 June 2021	RSBI	https://tinyurl.com/robioinfo10	online
12th @RoBioinfo Seminar: AI and ML in Science	5 July 2021	RSBI	https://tinyurl.com/robioinfo11	online
Biology meets code	25-26 May 2022	RSBI, hosted by the Platform for Research on Systemic Biology and Ecology, Bucharest	NA	In person

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Perspectives of Federated European Genome Archive in Romania	September 2022	Medical University, Timișoara	NA	In person
Workshop on data and methods infrastructures (Federated EGA & Galaxy)	13-14 December 2022	RSBI and ELIXIR Norway	NA	Online
Webinar: Procesarea datelor de secvențiere de nouă generație - Concepte introductive	9 February 2023	RSBI	https://rsbi.ro/eveniment/e/serie-de-seminarii-online/	Online
Procesarea datelor de secvențiere de nouă generație - Demo folosind platforma Galaxy	10 February 2023	RSBI	https://rsbi.ro/eveniment/e/serie-de-seminarii-online/	Online
Introduction to COSMIC, followed by some practical scenarios.	17 February 2023	RSBI	https://rsbi.ro/eveniment/e/serie-de-seminarii-online/	Online
Ensembl Genome browser	23 February 2023	RSBI	https://rsbi.ro/eveniment/e/serie-de-seminarii-online/	Online
Variant Effect Predictor	23 February 2023	RSBI	https://rsbi.ro/eveniment/e/serie-de-seminarii-online/	Online

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Whole exome sequencing versus Whole genome sequencing monogenic rare disease.	6 April 2023	RSBI	https://rsbi.ro/evenimente/serie-de-seminarii-online/	Online
Workshop Hands-on Pathogen Genomics	23-24 October 2023	Babes Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca	https://rsbi.ro/evenimente/workshop-on-hands-on-pathogen-genomics/	In person
Workshop Plotting Literacy for Genomics	27-28 November 2023	Babes Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca	https://rsbi.ro/evenimente/workshop-plotting-literacy-for-genomics/	In person
ELIXIR Norway Webinar Q&A about the structure and activity of a National Node	7 December 2023	RSBI	NA	online
Workshop on Taxonomic annotation of sequences using community-wide microbial genomics	14-16 February 2024	Babes Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca	https://rsbi.ro/evenimente/taxon-annot/	In person
Communities and Platforms in ELIXIR	7 March 2024	ELIXIR Hub	https://elixir-europe.org/events/elixir-romania-webinar	online
Common Workflow Language	10 April 2024	RSBI	https://rsbi.ro/evenimente/2024-robiinfo-conferinta/	In person

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Variant Interpretation - Tools and Resources	10 April 2024	RSBI	https://rsbi.ro/evenimente/2024-robioinfo-conferinta/	In person